

Optimal power generation mix modelling for Bangladesh up to 2050 considering nuclear and renewable options

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Abstract:

Access to affordable and clean energy is one of the basic requirements for sustainable growth. Bangladesh, being one of the developing nations, currently face a rapid growth in the electricity sector. However, this growth might cause energy security issues as natural gas, the main source of energy and electricity is depleting quickly and might be totally depleted by the next decade if no new gas-fields are discovered. Local and imported coal could be alternative to natural gas, which causes environmental pollution by emitting carbon di oxide and other greenhouse gases. Nuclear and renewable energy sources are also considered as future solution to the energy security problem though they have their specific technical limitations.

In this paper, we consider all available and potential energy sources for electricity generation taking into account their techno-economic limitations and apply the linear programming method to obtain the best generation mix which would ensure low cost and limited emission at the same time. The whole country is geographically divided in to nine regions to obtain high spatial resolution. In addition, hourly demand for all different nodes is projected so that high temporal resolution could be achieved for best optimization. This dynamic optimal power generation mix model provides optimized generation and capacity mix from 2020 to 2050 at five years interval. Different policy scenarios including carbon-emission limit and adaptation of new technologies has been considered for sensitivity analysis. This analysis provides a clear guideline for low-cost optimum electricity sector expansion planning for developing countries like Bangladesh which also promotes sustainable development.

Keywords:

Optimal Power Generation Mix Model (OPGM), Electricity, Fossil Fuel, Nuclear Power, Renewable Energy, Carbon Emission, Bangladesh.

1. Introduction

Bangladesh is a relatively small country with a huge population (165 million, 8th in the world) in the south Asia with potential to become the world's 23rd largest economy by 2050 in terms of projected gross domestic product (GDP) rankings at purchasing power parity (PPP) [1]. Bangladesh is also short-listed along with Vietnam and India as one of the three world's fastest growing economies over the period between 2016 and 2050. The country is going through a rapid, but stable economic growth over the last decade. It is mostly driven by small-medium level industries and commercial service sectors due to increase in activities because of mega infrastructure projects, youthful and working age population. The economic growth in turn has created ever-growing energy demand, especially in the electricity sector. People with access to electricity almost doubled from 47% in 2009 to 95% in 2019 [2] while per-capita electricity consumption also doubled. The government recognizes the demand and growth of the electricity sector and it has adopted Power System Master Plan (PSMP, 2016) [3]

to address the issue in a timely manner. However, the master plan prepared with assistance from foreign donor agencies, prescribes to rely mostly on imported coal as the primary energy source for electricity generation (~50% of the total generation) that arises concerns from energy security and environmental safety perspectives. Traditionally, the country has always depended on its indigenous natural gas as the major component of the energy mix. Indigenous coal resources have hardly been tapped due to high population density near coalmines and techno-economic limitations. As the natural gas, resources tend to deplete more and more due to over consumption, identification and utilization of new resources have become a necessity to ensure sufficient electricity to the industries and households in order to support the economic growth and improved lifestyle at the same time.

Until now contribution of developing countries, such as Bangladesh in greenhouse gas (GHG) emission and global warming is not significant. However, if the world fails to take timely and necessary actions to reduce CO₂ and other GHG emissions significantly, Bangladesh would be one of the countries to face the worst effects of climate change due to its geographical position. Projections infer that the costs to Bangladesh of climate change could amount to an annual loss of 2% of GDP by 2050 and 9.4% of GDP by 2100 [4]. As a part of the historic and ambitious international climate agreement at the U.N. framework convention on climate change (UNFCCC) conference of the parties (COP21) in Paris in December 2015, to reduce future emissions, Bangladesh set out the intended nationally determined contributions (INDC) goal from its perspective. According to the INDC of Bangladesh, the country would contribution to reduce GHG emissions by 5% unconditionally and 15% subject to international support (in the form of finance, investment, technology development-transfer, and capacity building) from business as usual (BAU) levels by 2030 in the power, transport and industry sectors, based on existing resources as a mitigation contribution [5] as detailed in Table 1.

Table 1: Projected emissions reductions in the power, transport, and industry by 2030

Sector	Base Year (2011) (MtCO ₂ e)	BAU scenario (2030) (MtCO ₂ e)	BAU change from 2011 to 2030	Unconditional contribution scenario (2030) (MtCO ₂ e)	Change Vs BAU	Conditional contribution scenario (2030) (MtCO ₂ e)	Change Vs BAU
Power	21	91	336%	86	-5%	75	-18%
Transport	17	37	118%	33	-9%	28	-24%
Industry	26	106	300%	102	-4%	95	-10%
Total	64	234	264%	222	-5%	198	-15%

The national commitment to reduce GHG emission in power sector and the future plan for electricity generation expansion in Bangladesh may not be in complete synchronization as huge growth is fossil fuel (especially coal) usage can hardly contribute in reducing CO₂ and other GHG emissions in BAU case. In this study, we analyse the present status of the electricity sector and sort out available indigenous fossil fuel and renewable resources including possibility to import of fuel and electricity. The project electricity demand is then fed to a linear optimization model to obtain the most economic energy mix for future generation considering all possible techno-economic constraints. Finally, different emission constraints are imposed to satisfy the INDC for 2030 and beyond so that alternate energy mix and expansion plan could be formulated for the sustainable development. The focus of this analysis is to obtain the contribution of clean energy sources like nuclear and renewables to replace traditional fossil fuel sources in the long-term electricity mix of the country. The cost of decarbonization is also calculated to observe the effect on the overall economy due to the transition in fuel-mix.

2. Energy and Electricity sectors of Bangladesh

The primary energy source of Bangladesh is the indigenous natural gas, which contributes more than half of the present demand. As the country transforming from agriculture to more industry and commercial service-oriented society, dependency on modern form of energy such as natural gas is increasing shifting from traditional biomass and wastes. Imported oil and petroleum products have a steady growth, mostly used in the transportation and power sector. Although there is a reserve of coal, a very small amount is used for primarily electricity generation. The overall contribution from the hydro, solar and other renewable sources are too small mostly due to techno-economic reasons.

Electricity is one of the cleanest forms of final energy due to ease in transmission and multiple applications. The electricity sector in Bangladesh is even more dependent on the natural gas due to low cost and stable supply of the indigenous resource. Presently, it accounts for almost 70% of the electricity generated in the country. Gas-based combined cycle power plants serve the base load whereas some gas engines and mostly oil-based rental power plants serve the variable peak load. Country's only hydro power plant in Kaptai, Ranganmati has a capacity of 230 MW with limited potential for growth due to geographical position. Distributed rooftop solar home systems mostly serve the off-grid areas whereas some grid-connected mini-solar and experimental wind turbines are also contributing to the overall electricity mix. In addition, electricity import from neighbour India is currently in action with present capacity of 1160 MW, with additional potential interconnections currently under construction, while negotiations are going on with Nepal and Bhutan to import clean hydroelectricity through India. The present electricity installed capacity and generation mix for the 2018-19 financial year [2] are presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. (a) Installed capacity and (b) electricity generation mix of Bangladesh in 2018-19.

Since first discovery in 1955 as of today 27 gas fields, 25 in the onshore and 2 in the offshore have been discovered in Bangladesh. Of them 20 gas fields are in production, one offshore gas field have depilated after 14 years of production while other offshore field has not been viable for production due to small reserve. The estimated proven plus probable recoverable reserve was 28.69 Tcf (Trillion cubic feet). As of June 2019, a total of 16.93 Tcf gas has already been produced leaving only 11.76 TCF recoverable reserve in proven plus probable category [6] which would be depleted by 2030 at present rate of consumption [7].

In Bangladesh, the reserve of coal (Bituminous Coal) is about 3 billion tones which is equivalent to 85 Tcf gas in 5 coal fields so far discovered. Coal might be the alternative fuel to natural gas that can conveniently meet the energy needs of Bangladesh for 50 years. The coal of Bangladesh is of high quality due to high calorific value and low Sulphur content. However, due to high population density near coal mines, this indigenous resource has hardly been utilized.

Other than natural gas and coal, the country has a good potential of solar energy which has so far been utilized in off-grid areas as solar home systems. The government had a plan to generate 500 MW of electricity from solar by 2020 which has been delayed due to financial and technical limitations. Now, the country is going for nuclear power and the construction of 2.4 GW nuclear power plant in Rooppur, Pabna is underway which is expected to start operation by 2024-25.

3. Methodology of linear optimization for generation expansion

To develop the model for optimal electricity generation expansion, we used linear programming to obtain the least cost generation mix for the hourly projected electricity demand considering different techno-economic and resource constraints. The electricity demand forecast was performed using MAED [8] with hourly load data derived from industry, household, service and transportation sectors based on economic growth for median variant population projections made by the UN department of economic and social affairs division [9]. Constraints regarding indigenous natural resources, potential for import of fossil fuel and renewable energy growth potential with relevant prices were considered as per available data from national and international sources. The total number of constraints was just over 30 million with about 10 million exogenous variables. The whole of Bangladesh was considered as a single node to reduce the calculation cost. IBM ILOG CPLEX optimization studio version 12.5 optimization software package was utilized to run the model for convergence in terms of linear optimization. Model parameters (exogenous variables) such as technical assumptions and output (endogenous variables) such as system cost, and carbon emission related to power generation and storage technologies are listed in Table 2, 3. The model formulation is based on previous work as detailed in [10-15].

Table 2 Endogenous variables

Variables	Definitions
TC	Total system cost [Billion \$];
$CO2em_y$	CO ₂ emissions in year y [Millions ton-CO ₂ /year];
$C_{y,i}$	Installed power capacity of i^{th} power plant type in year y [GW];
$C_{y,j}$	Installed power capacity of j^{th} storage technology type in year y [GW];
$EC_{y,j}$	Installed energy capacity of j^{th} storage technology type in year y [GWh];
$GE_{y,i}$	Annual energy generated from i^{th} power plant type in year y [GWh/year];
$SE_{y,j}$	Annual stored energy from j^{th} storage technology type in year y [GWh/year];
$P_{y,d,t,i}$	Power generated by i^{th} power plant type in day d , time step t and year y [GW];
$Pcha_{y,d,t,j}$	Power absorbed by j^{th} storage technology type in day d , time step t and year y [GW];
$Pdis_{y,d,t,j}$	Power discharged by j^{th} storage technology type in day d , time step t & year y [GW];
$NC_{y,i}$	Newly constructed power capacity of i^{th} power plant type in year y [GW];
$NC_{y,j}$	Newly constructed power capacity of j^{th} storage technology type in year y [GW];
$NEC_{y,j}$	Newly constructed energy capacity of j^{th} storage technology type in year y [GWh];
$A_{y,d,i}$	Available capacity of i^{th} power plant type in day d , year y [GW];
$MK_{y,m,i}$	Unavailable cap. of i^{th} power plant type in m^{th} maintenance schedule in year y [GW];
$SE_{y,d,t,i}$	Energy stored in i^{th} power plant type in day d , time step t and year y [GW];
$Psupp_{y,d,t,i}$	Power suppressed of i^{th} power plant type in day d , time step t and year y [GW];
$SE_{y,d,t,j}$	Energy stored in j^{th} storage technology type in day d , time step t and year y [GWh];
$DMax_{y,d,i}$	Maximum power output of i^{th} power plant type in day d , year y [GW];

where the indices are defined as follows throughout the paper unless otherwise mentioned

i	$\in \{1: \text{Hydro}, 2: \text{Nuclear}, 3: \text{Coal-fired}, 4: \text{Gas-fired}, 5: \text{Biomass}, 6: \text{Oil}, 7: \text{Solar}, 8: \text{Wind}\}$ i.e., power plants considered.
j	$\in \{1: \text{Battery}\}$ i.e., storage technology considered.
t	$\in \{1, 2, \dots, T\}$, T = number of time steps in a day [$T=24$].
d	$\in \{1, 2, \dots, D\}$, D = number of days in a year [$D=365$].
y	$\in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, Y\}$, Y = number of yearly time steps (points) [$Y=7$].
$year_y$	$c \{\text{year}_0: 2015, \text{year}_1: 2020, \text{year}_2: 2025, \text{year}_3: 2030, \text{year}_4: 2035, \text{year}_5: 2040, \text{year}_6: 2045, \text{year}_7: 2050, [S=5]$
m	$\in \{1, 2, \dots, M\}$ i.e., number of maintenance schedules considered [$M=4$].
Γ	\equiv Discount rate (%)

Table 3 Exogenous variables

Variables	Type	Nuclear	Coal	Gas	Biomass	Oil	Solar	Wind
$UCC_{y,i}$	Unit construction cost [USD/kW]	5000	2000	1500	1600	1200	1500~1000	2000~1500
LT_i	Lifetime [year]	45	40	30	30	30	20	30
IC_i	Initial installed capacity [GW]	0	0.5	6	0	3.0	0.5	0
	Specific unit	kWh	kg	kg	kg	liter	NA	NA
$FCS_{y,i}$	Fuel cost [USD/Specific unit]	0.025	0.10 ~ 0.13	0.45 ~ 0.60	0.05 ~ 0.06	0.50 ~ 0.65	0	0
HC_i	Heat content (Gross) [MJ/specific unit]	3.6	19.67	54.67	14.83	41.26	NA	NA
Eff_i	Efficiency ¹	1.00	0.40	0.52	0.22	0.39	NA	NA
OCR_i	Own consumption rate	0.04	0.062	0.02	0.04	0.045	NA	NA
CC_i	Carbon content [kg-C/specific unit]	0.00	0.51	0.746	0.003	0.788	0	0
SPA_i	Seasonal peak availability	0.816	0.797	0.882	0.74	0.860	0.78	0.97
AAA_i	Annual average availability	0.768	0.734	0.816	0.679	0.764	0.163	0.142

3.1. Objective function

The objective of the linear program model corresponds to the net present value of the overall power system cost (in billion \$) over the entire analysis period (2015 to 2050) at discounted value. It is formulated by Eq. (1), taken into considerations of the annual fixed cost (AFC_y) and annual variable cost (AVC_y) for different power generation and storage technologies. The external costs including transmission, distribution and cost for external infrastructure development are not considered here.

$$\min : TC = \sum_{y=0}^Y \sum_{s=0}^S \left(\frac{s}{(1+\Gamma)^{S \times y + s}} + \frac{(S-s)}{(1+\Gamma)^{S(y+1)+s}} \right) \times \frac{AFC_y + AVC_y}{S} \quad (1)$$

The annual fixed costs for a given year is estimated as the difference between installed power capacity and the remaining capacity (RC) from the base year in GW multiplied by capital recovery factor (CRF) and unit construction cost in USD/kW. It includes annualized value of the initial investment (construction cost), the operation and maintenance cost, the fixed asset taxes and the scrap value of the asset at the end of the lifetime of each power plants and storage technologies.

3.2. Constraints for optimization

3.2.1. Power demand and supply balances

This constraint infers that the total power generation from all generation technologies and storage medium should equal to the power demand at each time step. It is given by Eq. (2).

$$Load_{y,d,t} = \sum_{i=1}^8 P_{y,d,t,i} + (Pdis_{y,d,t} - Pcha_{y,d,t}) \quad (2)$$

3.2.2. Capacity constraints and maintenance schedule

This paper assumes four time-profiles of annual maintenance schedule as illustrated in Fig. 2 based on the formulation presented in [10].

¹ Thermal to electrical energy conversion efficiency for nuclear power plants has been incorporated in the heat content (gross) value.

Fig. 2. Four different patterns for shutdown of thermal power plants due to annual maintenance

3.2.3. Carbon emission constraints

The CO₂ emissions from thermal power plants are calculated at each time point and aggregated over the year to keep it within the emission levels at different scenarios according to Eq. (3).

$$CO_2em_y \leq CO_2emMax_y \quad (3)$$

3.2.4. Operational constraints

The output of various renewable power generation technologies are mostly dependent on seasonal, geographical and daily variations. Accordingly, capacity factors along with hourly availability of the generation technologies are defined based on historical data as shown in Fig.6 and Fig.7 for solar and wind power, respectively. The seasonal capacity variations of the local storage based hydro option is considered based on the availability of water at Kaptai dam. For the fluctuating renewable sources, output suppression is allowed to discard the excess electricity if it seems to be cheaper than adding more storage technologies.

3.2.5. Capacity reserve constraints for power supply reliability

To maintain electricity supply reliability, reserve capacity (10% in this case) is assured as per Eq. (4). The power supply of hydro, wind and PV is not considered in the capacity reserve due to its unpredictable output profile, although the certain ratio of PV output is reported to be expected.

$$\sum_{i=2}^6 A_{y,d,i} \geq (1 + \delta) \times Load_{y,d,t} \quad (4)$$

3.2.6. Minimum output level constraints

Most thermal power plant operates more than a minimum threshold, excluding thermal plant with DSS (Daily Start and Stop) mode. For sharp demand variations within a day, thermal plant with DSS mode generates electricity under rapid heat-up and cool-down cycle. Eq. (5-7) are applicable only to the thermal power plants except those working on DSS mode and is adopted from [10].

$$P_{y,d,t,i} \geq (DMax_{y,d,i} - A_{y,d,i} \times DSS_i) \times MOL_i; (i = 2, 3, 4, 5, 6) \quad (5)$$

$$DMax_{y,d,i} \geq P_{y,d,t,i} \quad (6)$$

$$DMax_{y,d,i} \geq P_{y,d+1,t,i} \quad (7)$$

3.2.7. Constraints on load following capability of power plants

Some power plant has its own load following capability, whereas some cannot change its output abruptly. The parameter CW is introduced to relax the load following constraints. Hydro power plants can slowly change its output level as illustrated in Eq. (8-11) account for the load following properties of each thermal power plant types. These mathematical formulations are also based on [10].

$$P_{y,d,t} \leq P_{y,d,t-1} + \text{increase} \times H \times (CF_d \times C_y \times CW_i \times P_{y,d,t-1} \times (1 - CW_i)) \quad (8)$$

$$P_{y,d,t} \geq P_{y,d,t-1} - \text{decrease} \times H \times (CF_d \times C_y \times CW_i \times P_{y,d,t-1} \times (1 - CW_i)) \quad (9)$$

$$P_{y,d,t,i} \leq P_{y,d,t-1,i} + \text{increase} \times H \times (A_{y,d,i} \times CW_i \times P_{y,d,t-1,i} \times (1 - CW_i)) \quad (10)$$

$$P_{y,d,t,i} \geq P_{y,d,t-1,i} - \text{decrease} \times H \times (A_{y,d,i} \times CW_i \times P_{y,d,t-1,i} \times (1 - CW_i)) \quad (11)$$

3.2.8. Charge and discharge balance of energy storage technology

Equation (12) explains the balance of power charge and discharge for stored electricity in a storage facility and formulated to illustrate the state of stored energy for batteries, which is governed by self-discharge rate and their round-trip storage efficiency. Charge cycle efficiency and discharge cycle efficiency of the battery are equal to the square root of the round-trip efficiency. The flexibility of charge and discharge is characterized by C-rate for a rechargeable battery such as NAS and Li-ion battery as illustrated in Eq. (13) and Eq. (14). In addition, Eq. (15) describes that the capability of power charging in a year is regulated by the annually possible charge-discharge cycles of rechargeable battery, where the left-hand side represents annual charged power into the battery and right-hand side shows annually storable power considering the annually possible charge-discharge cycles of the battery. These mathematical formulations are based on [10-15].

$$SE_{y,d,t,j} = SE_{y,d,t-1,j} \times (1 - SDL_j) + (Pcha_{y,d,t-1,j} \times \sqrt{Eff_j} - Pdis_{y,d,t-1,j} \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{Eff_j}}) \times H \quad (12)$$

$$EC_{y,j} \leq C_{y,j} \times MDC_j \quad (13)$$

$$C_{y,j} \leq EC_{y,j} \times CRT_j \quad (14)$$

$$\sum_{d=1}^D \sum_{t=1}^T Pcha_{y,d,t,j} \times H \leq EC_{y,j} \times CFE_j \times \frac{LC_j}{LT_j} \quad (15)$$

3.3. Electricity demand modelling

The electricity demand forecast for the years 2020 to 2050 at an interval was performed using MAED-2 model taking the actual load data of 2015 as the base year. The results of the analysis made in [16-17], as shown in Fig. 3 is used as the input for future load forecasting in this analysis. The seasonal variations and shift of demand shift from household to industry and commercial service sectors have been reflected in the changing patterns of the load curves over time. The business as usual growth scenario is considered for further analysis.

Fig. 3. Electricity demand projection for different socio-economic growth scenarios

4. Results and scenarios analysis

As the main focus of this analysis is to observe and validate different energy mix and carbon emission scenarios with respect to cleaner energy sources like nuclear and renewables, we consider three different emission scenarios namely business as usual (BAU), INDC case and 50% reduction case. The business as usual scenario considers the carbon emission scenario as depicted in the INDC of Bangladesh, where no emission controlling measures have been considered. This case refers to 91Mt CO₂e emission from the power sector in 2030. For this analysis, we extrapolate the BAU case up to the year 2050 at the value of 200Mt CO₂e. The Intended Nationally Determined Contributions or INDC case refers to the country's commitment to reduce the emission from power sector by 18% at 75Mt CO₂e by 2030 and then extrapolating the trend up to the final analysis year of 2050. It is to be noted that, we considered the conditional contribution scenario instead of the unconditional contribution scenario as the later would not necessarily be reflected in the generation mix change by reducing 5% emission only. The 50% reduction scenario confirms 50% reduction of CO₂ emission by the year 2050 with respect to the emission perceived in the BAU case. The historical data for CO₂ emission and projections for the three scenarios are presented in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Historical and projected CO₂ emissions for different scenarios

The linear programming model for optimum power generation and expansion used in this analysis takes into consideration technical limitations of the power system and different generation technologies. Moreover, it provides the least cost generation mix for all the analysis years satisfying hourly demand and yearly CO₂ emission limits. The current government policy for future electricity generation has been considered for all different emission scenarios incorporating local indigenous resources, potential for fuel, electricity import and incorporation of new technologies like nuclear power and battery storage. We present the results of electricity generation mix for different emission scenarios in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Optimum electricity generation-mix for (a) BAU, (b) INDC and (c) 50% reduction scenarios

The BAU case reflects the current generation plan of dependence on coal as the primary resource, which is also the least cost generation source even for imported fuel as the alternate fuel, indigenous natural gas would be depleted by 2030. The INDC scenario shows that nuclear potential is to be fully utilized take some share of the base load coal, whereas solar energy takes a major share of natural gas in the later years as CO₂ emission constraints take into action. The strict 50% reduction scenario utilizes almost full potential of the solar, nuclear natural gas options for deep de-carbonization.

Fig. 6. Year wise total installed capacity for electricity generation at different scenarios

If we take a close look on the year wise total installed capacity for different emission scenarios as shown in Fig. 6, it becomes prominent that the contribution from renewable energy sources is not that significant until the year 2040. However, after 2040 the contribution from solar and wind energy increases the total installed capacity by a significant amount, especially in the INDC and 50% reduction scenarios due to low capacity factor. The carbon emission targets mostly switch the base load from coal to nuclear and natural gas. As the government has started implementing almost 10GW coal-based projects and most of those would be connected to the grid by 2025, contribution from coal cannot be fully eliminated. With the INDC concerns, coal growth needs to be reduced almost fully by 2025. The current master plan [3] projects heavy rely on coal up to the year 2040, which would definitely find it difficult to keep the emission limited even in the BAU case. If the country necessarily wishes to continue with their CO₂ emission limit plan, then switching from coal to nuclear and even to costly LNG based generation is inevitable. Another important aspect of the capacity mix is that there are some oil-based plants and energy storage technologies present, most in the later time points. However, contribution from these fuel and storage sources are too small in the generation mix. These technologies mostly represent the capacity reserve part due to relatively low installation cost and the contribution remains insignificant due to high fuel and operational cost.

The switching to clear energy sources does come with a price. If we compare the total system cost for the three different emission scenarios, it is evident that the cost of BAU and INDC case are not that different. The reason is slight reduction in coal generation is good enough to maintain INDC emission level whereas the costly gas-based generation is shifted to cheaper nuclear generation at later years in addition to the higher solar output. Therefore, simple policy level update could bring the reduction in emissions to fulfil the promise made through INDC. However, reducing emissions by 50% with respect to the BAU scenario would increase the system cost by about 1.275%, i.e. equivalent to 3.622 billion USD. This difference also reflects another important issue regarding technology change and cost relationship. The learning rates of solar, wind and nuclear technologies are faster than already developed coal and gas-based technologies. As a result, even though the installed capacity increases for the emission limit scenarios, the system costs do not change that much as new technologies become cheaper. In connection with the first INDC, Bangladesh could update the next INDCs to accommodate higher level of voluntary or conditional higher emission limits as the overall impact on economy would be little.

Table 4 Total Power System cost for different emission scenarios

Emission Scenario	Total System Cost (Billion USD)	Change from BAU case
BAU	284.2917	-
INDC	284.4681	0.06 %
50% reduction	287.9135	1.274 %

As we observe that switching of technologies to clear and new technologies comes at the cost of economic loss, many of the developed countries have proposed and some already implemented the concept of carbon tax. However, the electricity market of Bangladesh is still fully regulated by the government and often subsidized. Introducing carbon-tax at a later stage, preferably after 2040 may reduce the burden on economy and encourage the consumer sector to use efficient and clean energy sources.

5. Conclusion and implications

This paper evaluates the optimal electricity generation mix of Bangladesh for different carbon emission scenarios using a dynamic hourly resolution optimal power generation mix model. The proposed model accommodates full potential of solar, wind and hydropower to reduce the carbon emission level in future generation mix. In addition, traditional fossil fuel-based resources were also considered with the scope of imported fuel as some resources deplete and others remain unusable for different regions. As nuclear power is also becoming popular in some of the developing regions of the world, gradual development of this sector is inevitable due to its very low carbon intensity. The optimized generation mix provide important information regarding policy level implications of different carbon emission strategies.

It is estimated that the demand of electricity would grow about eight times over the 35 years analysis period (from 2015 to 2050) even in the business as usual case. Under the circumstances, diversified energy sources reduce over dependence on single source, which requires huge investment and long-term commitment at the same time. As the country has committed INDC and set the maximum limit for the power sector, the strategy to achieve the goal needs to be well defined. In this analysis, we show that the INDC target is not too difficult to achieve by simple adjustments in the mix. Nevertheless, the INDC target is up to 2030 only. It might become difficult to change the trend for long-term planning up to the year 2050 when the demand and consumption reaches a significant higher level, so does the emissions. However, considering deep decarbonization at 50% reduction scenario for medium to long-term planning, renewable energy options like solar and wind are the best fit. Contribution of nuclear power also cannot be ignored as it takes the base load, which the intermittent renewable technologies cannot serve. The cost of decarbonization (~3.5 bl\$ for 50% reduction scenario) may not be too high if advance policy is adopted and executed accordingly.

Bangladesh is facing the same issues that developing countries face, where practical action plans are prescribed by donor agencies to fulfil their own objectives. The country's commitment to international community for reducing carbon emission may not be successful if it continues with the existing power system master plan heavily patronizing coal and other GHG emission intensive technologies. To save the world from the adverse effects of climate change and reduce carbon emission, even small but emerging countries like Bangladesh can play important role by incorporating modern nuclear and clean renewable energy technologies in a developing grid structure through regional cooperation and technology transfer.

References

- [1] Price Waterhouse Coopers International Limited (PWC), The World in 2050; 2017 Feb.
- [2] Bangladesh Power Development Board (BPDB), Annual Report 2018-2019; 2019 Oct. Available at: <https://bpdb.gov.bd/bpdb_new/resourcefile/annualreports/annualreport_1574325376_Annual_Report_2018-19.pdf> [accessed 1.1.2020].
- [3] Power Division, Ministry of Power, Energy and Mineral Resources (MPEMR), Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, Power System master Plan (PSMP), 2016 Sep.
- [4] Asian Development Bank (ADB), Assessing the Costs of Climate Change and Adaptation in South Asia, 2014 Jun.
- [5] Ministry of Environment and Forests (MOEF), Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, Intended Nationally Determined Contributions (INDC), 2015 Sep. Available at: <https://www4.unfccc.int/sites/ndcstaging/PublishedDocuments/Bangladesh%20First/INDC_2015_of_Bangladesh.pdf> [accessed 10.1.2020].
- [6] Hydrocarbon Unit (HCU), Energy and Mineral Resources Division, Ministry of Power, Energy and Mineral Resources; Energy Scenario Bangladesh 2018-19, 2020 Jan.
- [7] The Daily Star (TDS), Country's gas reserve will be exhausted in 11 years, January 20, 2020. Available at: <<https://www.thedailystar.net/country/news/countrys-gas-reserve-may-be-exhausted-11-years-nasrul-hamid-1856629>> [accessed 20.1.2020].
- [8] International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), Model for analysis of energy demand (MAED-2), 2006 Jan.
- [9] United Nations (UN), World population prospects, 2019 Jun.
- [10] Komiyama, R. and Fujii, Y., Assessment of massive integration of photovoltaic system considering rechargeable battery in Japan with high time-resolution optimal power generation mix model. *Energy Policy* 2014;66:73-89.
- [11] Komiyama, R. and Fujii, Y., Energy modelling and analysis for optimal grid integration of large-scale variable renewables using hydrogen storage in Japan. *Energy* 2015;81:537-555.
- [12] Komiyama, R. and Fujii, Y., Long-term scenario analysis of nuclear energy and variable renewables in Japan's power generation mix considering flexible power resources. *Energy Policy* 2015;83:169-184.
- [13] Komiyama, R. and Fujii, Y., Optimal Integration of Variable Renewables in Electric Power Systems of Japan. *J. Energy Eng.* 2016;10.1061/(ASCE)EY.1943-7897.0000361, F4016004.
- [14] Komiyama, R. and Fujii, Y., Assessment of post-Fukushima renewable energy policy in Japan's nation-wide power grid. *Energy Policy*, 2017;101:594-611.
- [15] Komiyama, R. and Fujii, Y., Optimal integration assessment of solar PV in Japan's electric power grid. *Renewable Energy*, 2019;139:1012-1028.
- [16] Sieed, J., Komiyama, R. and Fujii, Y., Energy Demand Modelling of Developing Economies Using MAED-2 with Sectoral Decomposition: Bangladesh Case Study, Proceedings of the 38th Research Presentation of Japan Society of Energy and Resources, Tokyo, Japan, 2019 Aug.
- [17] Sieed, J., Komiyama, R. and Fujii, Y., Long-term Projection of Hourly Electricity Demand with Sectoral Decomposition for Developing Economies: Bangladesh Case Study, Proceedings of the 36th Energy System, Economics, Environmental Conference, Tokyo, Japan, 2020 Jan.